

WDP: Mitigating Interference in CPU Sharing Through Wake-up Delay Driven Preemption for QoS-aware Co-location (pap235s2)

Supplementary materials for rebuttal

Comm1-Scalability and Industrial Deployment (Reviewer 1&4&5)

(a) The average 95%-ile latency of LC tasks

(b) The average Job Completion Time of BE tasks

Figure 1: The average tail latency of LC tasks and job completion time of BE tasks when co-running on 128 cores

We co-run 40 LC tasks and 21 BE tasks on a server equipped with INTEL XEON PLATINUM 8562Y+(128 cores with 2 NUMA nodes and DVFS/hyper-threading enabled). We use the same 5 LC tasks and 7 BE tasks as in the paper. Specifically, we run 8 instances for each of the 5 LC tasks and 3 instances for each of the 7 BE tasks. We keep task configurations consistent with those in our paper.

Figure 1 shows the tail latencies of LC tasks and the job completion times (JCT) of BE tasks. For better presentation, we show the average 95%-ile la-

tency/JCT of all instances for each LC/BE task.

As shown, WDP ensures QoS for all LC tasks and achieves higher BE throughput(lower JCT) compared to ARQ and CLITE. On average, WDP achieves 40.7% and 22.6% BE throughput improvement compared to CLITE and ARQ, respectively.

This experiment result shows that WDP scales well on many-core HPC servers, and is compatible with DVFS, hyper-threading, and the NUMA architecture.

Comm2-Overhead of WDP (Reviewer 2&3&4)

Overhead of eBPF hooks: As shown in Figure 10 in paper, hook1 and hook2 incurs overhead in the wake-up path while hook3 and hook4 incurs in the context-switch path.

We profile at 90% overall CPU utilization. For each hook, we profile 100k samples and calculate the 95% confidence interval(CI). The CIs(means) of time cost for hook1 and hook2 are 97-100ns(99ns) and 81-84ns(83ns), respectively. Invoked once per wake-up, they add 182ns to the Linux wake-up path whose CI of time cost is 5936-5974ns, representing less than 3% overhead. Hook2 cost scales with dispatch size. At a dispatch size of 128, Hook2’s CI is 160-161ns, keeping the maximum wake-up path cost at 260ns. The time cost CIs for hook3 and hook4 are 83-88ns and 44-47ns, respectively. Invoked once per context-switch, they add 133ns to the Linux context-switch path which costs 6423-6559ns.

Figure 2: The Context-switch times per second of BE tasks.

Overhead of increased context-switch: We profile the context-switch time of BE tasks in the experiment in Comm1. As shown in Figure 2, we compute the average context-switch times per second of all instances for each BE task. With system CPU utilization at 90%, compared to the unmanaged scenario, WDP incurs an average increase of 1.8 context-switch/s across all BE tasks, with a maximum increase of 11 context-switches/s with *bodytrack*. As a comparison, when taking the Linux real-time scheduler, the average increase is 44 context-switches/s, with a maximum increase of 202 context-switches/s with *blacksholes*.

WDP incurs limited context-switch increase compared to Unmanaged while still ensures QoS of all LC tasks. Compared to real-time scheduling, WDP incurs significant lower context-switch increase.

(a) The average 95%-ile latency of LC tasks

(b) The average Job Completion Time of BE tasks

Figure 3: The average tail latency of LC tasks and job completion time of BE tasks when co-running on 2 NUMA nodes

Comm3-WDP on NUMA (Reviewer 2&3)

Comm3.1-Root Cause of Interference under NUMA Architecture

We first prove that the wake-up delay is still the root cause of CPU interference in NUMA architecture. We rerun the experiment in Comm1 that co-runs 40 LC tasks and 21 BE tasks on 128 cores with 2 NUMA nodes.

While keeping all the configurations and CPU allocations the same as when WDP is enabled, we only disable the preemption mechanism that aims to eliminate the wake-up delay of LC tasks (marked as WDP_no_preemption in Figure 3).

As a result, as shown in Figure 3, without the preemption mechanism that eliminates the wake-up delay of LC tasks, all LC tasks experience severe QoS violations, resulting an average increase of 4.5x in 95%-ile latency.

This experiment shows that the wake-up delay is the root cause of interference (long tail latency) on the NUMA architecture.

Comm3.2-Enhancing WDP with NUMA-aware Scheduling Policy

We then demonstrate that WDP can be enhanced to work better on NUMA architecture. As an example, we enhance WDP to **WDP+** with the numa-aware scheduling strategy in [1]. Specifically, we enhance WDP in the following two aspects:

- When initially allocating cores to tasks, WDP prefers to allocate cores on the same NUMA node to a task.
- When migrating cores from other LC tasks to a QoS-violated LC task, WDP+ always prefers to migrate cores that are on the main NUMA node of the QoS-violated LC task. Following [1], we define the main NUMA node as the node storing the most data.

Algorithm 1 describe the scheduling logic of WDP+, which differs from the original algorithm in line 1 and lines 22-30;

Compared to WDP, WDP+ reduced the number of LC tasks that have cores across NUMA nodes from 14 to 2. As shown in Figure 3(a), applying WDP+ reduces the tail latency of LC tasks compared to WDP, achieving an average decrease of 13%.

Algorithm 1: Workflow of WDP+

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1 Initialize CPU resource allocation with NUMA-aware;
2 while True do
3   Monitor tail latency  $lat_i$  and CPU utilization  $U_i$  for each LC task $_i$  for a period;
4   for each LC task $_i$  do
5      $margin_i \leftarrow (QoS\_target_i - lat_i) / target_i$ ;
6     // Eliminating QoS violations of LC task
7     if there is an LC task $_i$  with minimal  $margin_i < 0$  then
8       if BE tasks do not share cores with task $_i$  then
9         Turn to manage other shared resources;
10      if LC task $_i$ 's dispatch size does not reach its maximum value then
11        Enable the preemption mechanism;
12        Gradually increase its dispatch size until  $margin_i > 0$ ;
13      else
14         $core\_donors \leftarrow \{\}$ ;
15        for each LC task $_j$  and task $_j$  is a qualified donor do
16           $core\_donors \leftarrow core\_donors \cup \{task_j\}$ ;
17        if  $core\_donors$  is empty then
18          if LC task $_i$  shares cores with BE tasks then
19            Stop sharing;
20          else
21            Turn to manage other shared resources;
22        else
23          for each donor in  $core\_donors$  sort by margin in descending order do
24            if donor has cores on the main NUMA node of task $_i$  then
25              if can safely migrate a core from donor to task $_i$  then
26                break;
27            if Successfully migrate a core to task $_i$  then
28              continue;
29            // No core on the main NUMA node available
30            for each donor in  $core\_donors$  sort by margin in descending order do
31              if can safely migrate a core from donor to task $_i$  then
32                break;
33      // Improve throughput of BE tasks
34      if All LC tasks meet their QoS requirements then
35        Find an LC task $_m$  with the maximum margin;
36        if task $_m$  does not share CPU cores with BE tasks then
37          Try to let task $_m$  share cores with BE tasks;
38        else
39          Gradually decreasing its dispatch size but keeping  $margin_m > 0$ ;
40          if its dispatch size == 0 and  $margin_m > 0$  then
41            Try disabling the preemption mechanism;

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1 Reviewer-1-D1 Experiment Results with Other BE tasks in Figure 2

We provide the plot of experiment results with other BE tasks in Figure 2. Our conclusion that existing tools cannot efficiently mitigate CPU interference while achieving high BE throughput still holds for other BE tasks.

Figure 4: Co-locating *blackscholes* with five different LC tasks, respectively. The upper part shows the JCT of *blackscholes* (the lower the better). The lower part shows the 95%-ile latency of the LC task, with the red line indicating the QoS target.

Figure 5: Co-locating *ferret* with five different LC tasks, respectively.

Figure 6: Co-locating *fluidanimate* with five different LC tasks, respectively.

Figure 7: Co-locating *streamcluster* with five different LC tasks, respectively.

Figure 8: Co-locating *stream* with five different LC tasks, respectively.

Figure 9: Co-locating *swaptions* with five different LC tasks, respectively.

Reviewer-1-D8 Experiment Results with Other LC tasks in Figure 11a

We provide the plot of LC tail latencies with other BE tasks in Figure 11a. WDP ensures QoS for all LC tasks when co-running with varied BE tasks.

Figure 10: The 95%-ile latency and JCT when co-running 5 LC tasks with *blackscholes*

Figure 11: The 95%-ile latency and JCT when co-running 5 LC tasks with *ferret*

Figure 12: The 95%-ile latency and JCT when co-running 5 LC tasks with *fluidanimate*

Figure 13: The 95%-ile latency and JCT when co-running 5 LC tasks with *streamcluster*

Figure 14: The 95%-ile latency and JCT when co-running 5 LC tasks with *stream*

Figure 15: The 95%-ile latency and JCT when co-running 5 LC tasks with *swaptions*

Reviewer-1-D14 Experiment Results with Real-time scheduling in Figure 13

We provide the plot of experiment results with real-time scheduling in Figure 13.

Figure 16: The JCT of *swaptions* when co-running with 5 LC tasks under different loads. The lighter the color, the better.

References

- [1] Pu Pang, Yaoxuan Li, Bo Liu, Quan Chen, Zhou Yu, Zhibin Yu, Deze Zeng, Jingwen Leng, Jieru Zhao, and Minyi Guo. Pac: Preference-aware co-location scheduling on heterogeneous numa architectures to improve resource utilization. In *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Supercomputing*, pages 75–86, 2023.